

Studies on Dichlorothioindigoid Dyes. Part I.**2-(4 : 7/6 : 7-Dichloro)thionaphthene-3'-indole indigos**

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MANY variations have been effected by differently substituting the thioindoxyl moiety of the dyes with a view to studying the consequent changes in absorption.

The present communication reports the preparation and properties of 2-(4 : 7-dichloro) thionaphthene-3'-indole indigos and 2-(6 : 7-dichloro)-thionaphthene-3'-indole indigos. It will be seen that one chlorine atom is substituted at either 4 or 6 position when second chlorine atom is retained at 7-position of the thionaphthene system.

For this purpose, 2,5-dichloro-1-phenylthioglycolic acid and 2,3-dichloro-1-phenylthioglycolic acid were prepared and cyclised to yield 4 : 7-dichlorothioindoxyl and 6 : 7-dichlorothioindoxyl respectively—all the four compounds are being reported for the first time.

These thioindoxyls were then condensed with isatin and its derivatives to afford a number of new thioindigoid dyes listed below. The general structure of the dyes can be represented as series A and B.

2-(Dichloro)thionaphthene-3'-indole indigo

Series A : 4 : 7-Dichloro Series B : 6 : 7-Dichloro

A ₁ , B ₁ : 5'-H	A ₅ , B ₅ : 5' : 7'-Dibromo
A ₂ , B ₂ : 5'-Cl	A ₆ , B ₆ : 5' : 7'-Bromonitro
A ₃ , B ₃ : 5'-Br	A ₇ , B ₇ : 5' : 7'-Dinitro
A ₄ , B ₄ : 5'-I	

The dyes belonging to the series A and B are soluble in pyridine, aniline and nitrobenzene. All the dyes mentioned here have been recrystallised from nitrobenzene. The dyes dissolve in concentrated sulphuric acid producing characteristic colours and the original dyes are reprecipitated on treatment with water. The dyes dissolve in alkaline hydrosulphite at 50°-60° producing light yellow or yellow vat and the original colour was developed on cotton when exposed to air.

Absorption maxima of the dyes were determined in pyridine solution on a Hilger Watts' spectrophotometer and are recorded in Table 1. The dyed shade on cotton, m.p.'s, % yield and the colours formed with conc. H₂SO₄ by the different dyes are also recorded in Table 1.

A scrutiny of the results show that in the 4 : 7-dichlorothioindigoid dyes the bathochromic effect is maximum.

The influence of different substituents in the isatin part of the dye molecule on absorption maximum of the dye has been studied in each series (Table 1). The 5'-chloro, 5'-bromo and 5'-iodo indole indigos absorbed at slightly longer wavelengths compared to the unsubstituted dyes whereas a small hypsochromic shift is observed in the case of 5'-iodo derivatives when compared with 5'-chloro and 5'-bromo dyes. The wavelengths of the absorption maxima of both the series are in the following order :

5' : 7'-Dinitro dye > 5'-bromo : 7'-nitro dye > 5' : 7'-dibromo dye > 5'-chloro dye > 5'-bromo dye > 5'-iodo dye > unsubstituted dye.

Experimental

2 : 5-Dichloro-1-phenylthioglycolic acid : A solution of sodium nitrite (8.4 g) in water (15 ml) was added dropwise to a stirred solution of 2 : 5-dichloroaniline (16.2 g) in concentrated hydrochloric acid (30 ml) and water (90 ml) at 0°-2°. The diazo solution was added during 30 mins. to a stirred solution of potassium xanthate (24 g), anhydrous sodium carbonate (48 g) and water (200 ml) kept on a water bath at 60°-80°. After a further hour stirring, the mixture was set aside overnight and then extracted with ether. The brown oily liquid, after the removal of ether, was refluxed for one hour with a mixture of sodium hydroxide (21 g), water (42 ml), and ethanol (135 ml).

A solution of monochloroacetic acid (18.8 g) in aqueous sodium hydroxide (10%, 85 ml) was added and the boiling continued for another hour. Ethanol was removed by distillation and the required acid was precipitated in cold with strong hydrochloric acid. The acid (14 g) was recrystallised from boiling water (bone charcoal) in pale brown colour, m.p. 125°. (Found : C, 40.35; H, 2.62%. Calcd. for C₈H₆O₂Cl₂S, C, 40.5; H, 2.53%).

4 : 7-Dichlorothioindoxyl : A mixture of 2 : 5-dichloro-1-phenylthioglycolic acid (5 g), chlorobenzene (35 ml) and phosphorus trichloride (10 ml) was stirred and refluxed at 70° for 2 hrs. The temperature was brought down and powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride (10 g) was added in small quantities at a time. The mixture was warmed and maintained at 60° for 3 hrs. The mixture was cooled and poured over ice (50 g). Chlorobenzene was removed by steam distillation. On further distillation with superheated steam and on cooling the distillate 4 : 7-dichlorothioindoxyl (1.04 g) separated, which was recrystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 60°-80°), m.p. 135°. (Found : C, 43.91; H, 1.74%. Calcd. for C₈H₄OCl₂S, C, 43.83; H, 1.82%).

TABLE I

Dyes	Yield (%)	M.P. °C	Colour in Conc. H ₂ SO ₄	Shade on cotton	Pyridine λ max
A ₁	70.9	> 315	Deep violet	Chocolate	498
B ₁	79.0	309	Brown	Orange	491
A ₂	62.7	> 315	Deep violet	Reddish violet	501
B ₂	78.4	> 320	Violet brown	Pink	494
A ₃	65.6	312	Deep violet	Reddish violet	500
B ₃	79.6	> 315	Reddish brown	Reddish brown	493
A ₄	67.5	305	Deep violet	Pink	499
B ₄	80.2	> 315	Brownish red	Orange red	492
A ₅	73.1	> 310	Dark violet	Dark pink	505
B ₅	75.1	302	Violet brown	Pink	500
A ₆	73.1	295	Dark violet	Reddish brown	508
B ₆	72.0	> 315	Violet brown	Reddish brown	504
A ₇	73.5	> 315	Dark violet	Pinkish violet	510
B ₇	57.1	> 315	Reddish violet	Pink	506

2:3-Dichloro-1-phenylthioglycollic acid: This compound was prepared similarly as described above, yield: 13 g; recrystallised from hot water (norite), m.p. 130.5°. (Found: C, 40.64; H, 2.65%. Calcd. for C₈H₆O₂Cl₂S, C, 40.5; H, 2.53%).

6:7-Dichlorothioindoxyl: A mixture of pure 2,3-dichloro-1-phenylthioglycollic acid (10 g) dissolved in chlorobenzene (60 ml) was heated at 70° with phosphorus trichloride (6 ml) and stirred continuously for 1½ hours. Powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride (20 g) was added to the cold product. The temperature was maintained at 65° for 3 hrs. with constant stirring. The cold mixture was added to ice (100 g) and the chlorobenzene removed in steam. On distillation with superheated steam, 6:7-dichlorothioindoxyl (1.67 g) was obtained which was crystallised from petroleum ether, b.p. 60°–80°, m.p. 169°. (Found: C, 43.76; H, 1.88%. Calcd. for C₈H₄OCl₂S, C, 43.83; H, 1.82%).

Preparation of dyes: The general method for the preparation of these dyes has been the condensation of the reactants in equimolecular proportion in boiling glacial acetic acid in presence of a small amount of concentrated hydrochloric acid for 10 mins. The dye was filtered, washed with boiling water and recrystallised from suitable solvents. Satisfactory analyses were obtained for all the compounds.

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Structural Study of the Anthraquinone Glycoside from the Flowers of *Morinda citrifolia*

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IN an earlier communication¹ isolation of two flavone-glycosides and an anthraquinone glycoside from the flowers of *Morinda citrifolia* along with the structural studies of the flavone glycosides had been reported.

The present communication deals with the structural studies of the anthraquinone glycoside.

The anthraquinone glycoside, C₂₉H₂₄O₁₄, m.p. 230°, when hydrolysed with ethanolic hydrochloric acid, gave an orange coloured aglycone C₁₇H₁₄O₆ (m.p. 210°) along with D(+)-glucose and L(-)-rhamnose (paper chromatography and TLC). The colour reactions and spectral properties of the aglycone were like those of an anthraquinone. The anthraquinone skeleton was further supported by isolation of 2-methyl anthracene from its zinc dust distillation product. The compound formed a monoacetate showing the presence of one hydroxyl group. It was found to have two methoxyl groups² (Zeisel; I.R. at 2890 cm⁻¹). The ethanolic solution of the compound formed a complex with ethanolic copper sulphate showing the presence of a hydroxyl function in α -position to the >C=O function³. The presence of only α -hydroxyl group is also supported by the peaks at 1630 cm⁻¹ and 1678 cm⁻¹ in the infra-red spectrum and λ max at 410 nm in the UV spectrum